

Vascular endothelial growth factor-C increases lymphatic vessels in the conjunctiva and maintains low intraocular pressure after trabeculectomy in rabbits

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to determine the effect of Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor-C (VEGF-C) in stimulating the growth of functional lymphatic vessels of postoperative conjunctival filtration blebs in rabbits. Twelve New Zealand Red Eye rabbits were allocated to four treatment groups, each receiving an injection of recombinant VEGF-C at doses of 0 µg (control), 1 µg, 3 µg, and 10 µg following trabeculectomy surgery. The effects of the VEGF-C injection on lymphatic vessels were analyzed using FLT4 fluorescence immunostaining and trypan blue filling techniques. Additionally, vascular vessels were examined using CD31 immunostaining, and post-surgical intraocular pressure (IOP) was compared across the treatment groups. Lymphatic vessels in treatment groups exhibited higher mean values of 11.7, 12.7, and 19.0 in groups treated with 1 µg, 3 µg, and 10 µg of VEGF-C, respectively, compared to a mean value of 5.3 in the control group ($p = 0.00$). Blood vessel count revealed using CD31 did not indicate any increase in vascular vessels between the groups. Intraocular pressure (IOP) levels ten days after trabeculectomy were significantly lower in the 3 µg and 10 µg treatment groups (7.00 mmHg) compared to 10.33 mmHg in the control group ($p = 0.047$). The study demonstrates that trabeculectomy augmented with VEGF-C injection in rabbits results in an increased lymphatic vessel count in the conjunctiva and a decrease in IOP levels on the tenth post-operative day. These findings suggest that VEGF-C may be a potential adjuvant agent for enhancing the efficacy of trabeculectomy.

Keywords

lymphatic vessels, conjunctiva, trabeculectomy, vascular endothelial growth factor-C, intraocular pressure

Introduction

Trabeculectomy surgery is the primary surgical treatment for glaucoma, offering long-term reduction of intraocular pressure (IOP) and prevention of optic nerve damage (Jaais 2004; Koike and Chang 2018). However, the efficacy of trabeculectomy in maintaining reduced IOP diminishes over time. Numerous factors contribute to this declining success rate, with conjunctival scarring and fibrosis being significant contributors (de Fendi et al. 2016).

The presence of lymphatic vessels in the conjunctiva has been implicated in the outcome of trabeculectomy. It is postulated that a viable and abundant lymphatic system in the conjunctiva may enhance bleb function following trabeculectomy by facilitating the drainage of fluid from the subconjunctival space (Singh et al. 2003; Yu et al. 2009; Khoo et al. 2019). The growth of lymphatic vessels is promoted by Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor-C (VEGF-C), a member of the vascular endothelial growth factor family, which also includes other vascular endothelial growth factors (VEGF-A, VEGF-B, and VEGF-D). Recent studies have investigated VEGF-C for its ability to stimulate lymphatic vasculature development in the conjunctiva (Lee et al. 2022; Rasic et al. 2023). However, the potential impact of VEGF-C on the lymphatic system following trabeculectomy surgery remains unexplored.

The objective of this study is to investigate the impact of VEGF-C injection on the lymphatic vessels in the conjunctiva and its role in sustaining reduced IOP following trabeculectomy surgery in a rabbit model. To the best of our knowledge, this represents the pioneering study to explore the effects of VEGF-C on the conjunctiva following surgical intervention in an animal model.

Methods

This study is an animal experimental research study conducted in triplicate, adhering to the institutional principles of animal research standards and approved by the Ethical Research Committee of Dr. Saiful Anwar Hospital—Malang. Twelve healthy New Zealand Red Eye Rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*), aged 5 to 6 months, were randomly assigned to four treatment groups (three rabbits per group), including a control group (without VEGF-C injection) and three VEGF-C injection groups at doses of 1 µg, 3 µg, and 10 µg. Prior to the study commencement, a veterinarian examined the animals, excluding those exhibiting signs of ocular or systemic disease. Each rabbit was kept in a separate cage in an indoor facility with active air conditioning. Humidity was controlled at 50%–60%, with air temperature set at 20 °C. Feeding was provided *ad libitum*, and a five-day period of acclimatization was given for all animals before the commencement of surgical treatment.

All rabbits underwent partial-thickness scleral flap trabeculectomy surgery in the right eye, as described by Cairns (Salim 2012), followed by the injection of variable VEGF-C doses (Abbexa™ Rabbit VEGF-C Recombinant) into the

subconjunctival surgical site. Anesthesia for the surgery was obtained using systemic ketamine 35 mg/kg body weight in 0.5–1.0 ml intramuscular injection combined with 5 drops of 2% topical lidocaine. A single surgeon performed the trabeculectomy throughout the study. IOP measurements were taken using a Suoer™ Rebound Tonometer prior to surgery, on day one post-surgery, and on day ten post-surgery. On day ten post-surgery, trypan blue dye was injected into the bleb, and the presence of large lymphatic vessels was observed and counted using a Topcon OMS-90™ eye surgical microscope. Subsequently, the rabbits were sacrificed, and the operated eye was enucleated. The sclera and conjunctiva at the surgical site were incised for histological examination. Immunofluorescence microscopy with FLT-4 antibody (MedikBio™) was used to examine conjunctival lymphatic vessels, while vascular vessels were counted separately using CD-31 immunostaining antibody (Bioss™). The number of visible vessels from five separate fields under 100 × magnification was compared between treatment groups.

Animal care and surgical procedures were conducted in the Experimental Animal Development Laboratory. Histological slide preparation and immunostaining were performed at the Anatomical Pathology Department and Central Biomedical Laboratory, respectively. All facilities were located within the Faculty of Medicine Universitas Brawijaya in Malang.

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS ver. 20 (IBM™) to compare the means of lymphatic vessels stained with FLT-4, conjunctival vasculature stained with CD-31, trypan blue-filled conjunctival lymphatics, and IOP measurement differences between groups.

Results and discussion

Lymphatic vessels in the conjunctiva can be visualized using FLT-4 immunostaining and labeled with a secondary antibody that emits green fluorescence (shown in Fig. 1). The number of these lymphatic vessels was quantified in 5 microscopic fields of view under 100 × magnification. The mean quantity of lymphatic vessels in the control group was found to be lower at 5.3, compared to those of the treatment groups, which exhibited mean values of 11.7, 12.7, and 19.0 in groups treated with 1 µg, 3 µg, and 10 µg of VEGF-C, respectively (shown in Fig. 2). These differences were analyzed using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and determined to be statistically significant ($p = 0.00$). Moreover, Tukey post hoc analysis confirmed significant differences across all groups ($p = 0.00$ to $p = 0.002$), indicating a dose-related effect of the VEGF-C treatment.

Vascular number in the conjunctiva was also identified and counted using CD31 immunostaining followed with a secondary antibody that emits red fluorescence. Conjunctival blood vessels are easily distinguishable, tending to be more rounded with thicker walls compared to lymphatics. In the analyzed samples, a slight decrease in vascular count was observed between control and treatment groups (shown in Fig. 3). Fig. 4 presents the mean values of vascular count,

Figure 1. Conjunctival lymphatic vessels (white arrows) after trabeculectomy observed with FLT-4 immunostaining under an immunofluorescent microscope alongside their phase-contrast image. **a.** Control group; **b, c, d.** With VEGF-C subconjunctival injection doses of 1 μ g, 3 μ g, and 10 μ g, respectively. Lymphatic vessels in VEGF-C-treated groups are more abundant in each microscopic field of view (observed with 100 \times magnification).

Figure 2. Number of conjunctival lymphatic vessels in control and VEGF-C-treated groups in five microscopic fields of view.

with the control group exhibiting a mean value of 11.33, while the treatment groups' means were 9.00, 8.67, and 9.00 for VEGF-C concentrations of 1 μ g, 3 μ g, and 10 μ g, respectively. One-way ANOVA analysis did not reveal any significant differences between groups ($p = 0.24$).

Trypan blue dye was injected into the filtering bleb 10 days post-surgery to visualize lymphatic vessels in a subset of rabbits (shown in Fig. 5). However, the number of observable lymphatics was limited, ranging from 0 to 3 vessels per rabbit. Although there was a trend towards increased visibility of conjunctival lymphatics in the VEGF-C treatment groups, the differences were not statistically significant.

IOP was measured at three different time points using a rebound tonometer: prior to surgery, one day post-surgery, and 10 days post-surgery. Mean IOP levels are shown in Fig. 6, Table 1. Generally, trabeculectomy surgery effectively reduced IOP on day 1 post-surgery, and this reduced IOP persisted after ten days. However, on day 10 post-surgery, the mean IOP in the treatment groups

Table 1. Mean intraocular pressure (IOP) in control and VEGF-C-treatment groups before and after trabeculectomy surgery.

Treatment Group	Mean IOP (Std. Dev) in mmHg		
	Before Surgery	Day 1	Day 10
Control	12.33 (0.58)	11.67 (2.08)	10.33 (1.53)
VEGF-C 1 μ g	12.00 (1.00)	9.67 (1.15)	8.00 (1.00)
VEGF-C 3 μ g	11.00 (1.00)	9.67 (0.58)	7.00 (1.73) *
VEGF-C 10 μ g	14.33 (1.15)	11.33 (2.08)	7.00 (0.00) *

* Indicates significant statistical difference compared to control in the same day with $p = 0.047$.

receiving VEGF-C doses of 3 μ g and 10 μ g was significantly lower compared to the control group ($p = 0.047$).

Trabeculectomy, introduced more than fifty years ago, remains the standard surgical procedure for glaucoma treatment. The procedure achieves normal and low intraocular pressure by diverting the aqueous pathway from the trabecular meshwork to a direct trans-scleral route into the subconjunctival space, forming a bleb (Koike and Chang 2018). However, as the subconjunctival space is not initially designed to contain a large volume of fluid, a mechanism must exist to remove this fluid from the bleb site and return it to circulation. The presence of lymphatics in the conjunctiva provides a natural explanation for this fluid flow mechanism, as one of the primary functions of the lymphatic system is to remove excess fluid from extracellular spaces (Breslin et al. 2019). In 2003; Singh described the presence of lymphatic systems related to blebs after trabeculectomy and suggested a possible correlation with the function of the filtering bleb (Singh et al. 2003). Yu et al. have also detailed the crucial role of the conjunctival lymphatic system in the success of glaucoma filtering surgery (Yu et al. 2009). Furthermore, Guo et al. quantified the topography of these

Figure 3. Vascular vessels in conjunctiva after trabeculectomy observed with an immunofluorescent microscope (CD-31 immunostaining) alongside their phase-contrast image; vascular walls are thicker and tend to be more rounded and easily identified (white arrows), sometimes with visible blood cells inside the lumen. **a.** Control group; **b, c, d.** With VEGF-C subconjunctival injection doses of 1 µg, 3 µg, and 10 µg, respectively. There are no clear differences in vascular count between control and treatment groups (observed with 100 × magnification).

Figure 4. Number of conjunctival vascular vessels in control and VEGF-C-treated groups in five microscopic fields of view.

Figure 5. Rabbit conjunctival lymphatics (black arrows) originating from the bleb seen with trypan blue filling under the eye surgical microscope (10 times magnification) on day ten after trabeculectomy. **a.** Control group; **b, c, d.** With VEGF-C subconjunctival injection doses of 1 µg, 3 µg, and 10 µg, respectively. Rabbits treated with VEGF-C tend to have more visible lymphatic vessels.

Figure 6. Graph showing mean intraocular pressure (IOP) in control and VEGF-C-treatment groups before and after trabeculectomy surgery. After 10 days, the mean IOP of treatment group 3 µg and 10 µg were significantly lower compared to the control group ($p = 0.047$).

conjunctival lymphatics in monkeys (Guo et al. 2012). Clinical studies have analyzed the relationship between lymphatic presence in patients who underwent trabeculectomy and IOP control (Bouhenni et al. 2016; Khoo et al. 2019). These studies collectively indicate that the quantity of lymphatic vessels in the conjunctiva is likely a significant factor in the long-term success of trabeculectomy.

Conversely, research on VEGF-C as the primary stimulator of lymphatic development has also been conducted in laboratory settings (Rauniyar et al. 2018). Recent studies have evaluated the positive effect of VEGF-C on the development of lymphatic vessels in the conjunctiva (Lee et al. 2022; Rasic et al. 2023). Our study expands on these previous findings, aiming to analyze whether

VEGF-C-stimulated lymphatic growth occurs after surgical intervention and if these stimulated lymphatics correlate with bleb function and, ultimately, IOP reduction. Trabeculectomy involves surgically incising the conjunctiva and sclera, creating an inflammatory environment for wound healing. Additionally, aqueous flow from the anterior chamber of the eye influences the healing of this delicate tissue post-surgery. The effects of externally injected VEGF-C into the subconjunctiva must be studied in this setting before clinical application. We chose to conduct this experimental study in rabbits due to the ease of simulating actual trabeculectomy surgery and elucidating the presence of lymphatic structures. The results of this study align with previous findings, confirming that VEGF-C stimulates lymphatic vessel growth. Furthermore, we demonstrated that this lymphatic growth occurs after surgical intervention in the conjunctiva and may positively affect the creation of a more functional bleb.

This study also evaluates the effect of VEGF-C on vascular vessels. In contrast to lymphatics, hypervascularization is considered detrimental to the proper functioning of a bleb, as it promotes earlier fibrosis (Yin et al. 2018; Akiyama et al. 2020; Schneider et al. 2024). Furthermore, VEGF-C is a growth factor within the VEGF family, which includes VEGF-A, a potent stimulator of neovascularization. Both VEGF-C and VEGF-A appear to share similar molecular structures that may allow for cross-reactivity between their receptors (Rauniyar et al. 2018). However, our results demonstrate that the number of vascular counts did not increase in the treatment groups; in fact, it slightly decreased compared to the control group. A possible explanation for this finding is that VEGF-C does not stimulate vascular growth as strongly as its VEGF-A counterpart. Additionally, in inflammatory conditions, the presence of more VEGF-C may reduce the potency of VEGF-A stimulation through competitive inhibition at their receptors.

In addition to histological examination, we also attempted to assess the visibility of lymphatic vessels in the conjunctiva following trabeculectomy in rabbits using trypan blue filling. This observational method has been previously described in other studies (Singh et al. 2003; Khoo et al. 2019). While the results of the lymphatic visibility count with trypan blue filling in this study showed some increase in visible lymphatics, they did not align with the significant difference found using the immunostaining method. This discrepancy is likely due to the fact that trypan blue filling primarily visualizes larger lymphatic vessels, and the limited observation period of ten days after surgery and VEGF-C injection in our study may not have captured the complete growth of larger lymphatics in the conjunctiva.

The lower IOP observed in rabbits treated with VEGF-C at doses of 3 µg and 10 µg on day 10 post-trabeculectomy underscores the potential utility of these substances as adjuvant treatments during or following surgical interventions involv-

ing the conjunctiva. IOP elevation can occur as early as one week after trabeculectomy due to the onset of bleb fibrosis, and numerous studies have investigated adjuvant substances that may minimize this process (Min et al. 2012; Nurwasis et al. 2020; Jiang et al. 2023). Seetner and Morin demonstrated that the filtering bleb fistula in rabbits can be completely closed due to fibrosis 14 days after trabeculectomy (Seetner and Morin 1979). In the present study, the IOP of rabbits receiving VEGF-C treatment was significantly lower 10 days post-surgery compared to one day after the procedure, representing a promising initial observation. However, further research is necessary to determine whether this IOP difference persists over an extended observation period.

The limitations of this study include the time constraint for the evaluation of IOP, as the rabbits were sacrificed on day ten to facilitate histological observation of lymphatic and vascular development and inflammatory reactions. To comprehensively assess the treatment's effects, a larger animal group with an extended in vivo observation period, potentially spanning several months, would be necessary. Additionally, this study did not induce IOP elevation or create a glaucoma model in the rabbits prior to surgery, which may have more closely resembled the conditions in glaucoma. However, as this is an initial study evaluating VEGF-C after surgically induced conditions, the induction of IOP, which might have masked the inflammatory effects of the surgery, was deemed unnecessary at this stage.

Conclusion

This study corroborates prior research on the effective propagation of lymphatic vessels in the conjunctiva and advances the field by applying this technique to surgically treated rabbit eyes. The reduced IOP achieved by combining VEGF-C injections with trabeculectomy suggests a potential role for the newly formed lymphatic vessels. Moreover, VEGF-C did not stimulate vascular vessel proliferation beyond what was observed with surgical stimulation alone. However, additional factors require further investigation, including the impact of VEGF-C on inflammation and wound healing following trabeculectomy.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Ethical Research Committee of Dr. Saiful Anwar Hospital – Malang with approval letter number: 400/ 37/ K-3/ 102-7/ 2024.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

Aulia A.H. Abdullah: Study design and execution, main manuscript writing and editing. Hidayat Sujuti: Study design, manuscript review and editing. Happy K. Permatasari: Study design, manuscript review and editing. Ihda D. Kusuma: Pathology data collection, manuscript review. Nurdiana: Study design, manuscript review and editing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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